

Food Donation and Food Waste Management Website

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Abstract:- The project is a website called FeedingHope, which works as a bridge between various restaurants and NGOs to manage leftover food. The amount of edible food that many restaurants dump in the garbage, Such food can be managed by donating to needy people, such as homeless people. So many NGOs encourage this type of activity. This website helps to find more and more restaurants that are willing to donate leftover food and NGOs who are interested in volunteering to pick up food and distribute it among the homeless people. The website is developed using HTML, and CSS for the front end and PHP, JavaScript, Bootstrap, and MySQL for the back end. The website will be hosted on the 000webhost platform, it is a free platform for students or any people who wants to host the website for free by uploading the project folder on the site. This website works on the donor and volunteer concept, where the donor is a restaurant and the volunteer is an NGO. The donor will make a request and the nearby volunteer accepts the request and picks up the food and distributes it to the homeless people. The user can become a part of our website by registering on our website.

Keywords:- HTML-Hypertext Markup Language, CSS-Cascading Style Sheet, NGO-National Governmental Organization, PHP-Hypertext Preprocessor, MySQL-Structured Query Language.

I. INTRODUCTION

Wastage of food not only harms the individuals of nations but the economy and the environment. India ranks 100 among the 119 countries. Our traditions and culture play a major role in these situations where the policies of the government aren't responsible for such waste. Here in India,

the bigger the wedding, the bigger the food wastage[1], Same with the Restaurants and hotels which produce or dump a large amount of edible food on daily basis. Our project will work as an intermediate between such restaurants and the NGOs or the volunteers who are interested in delivering the leftovers to those in need., because such an 'NGO' main job is to do social work. The amount of edible food that gets wasted, Instead of throwing it up, we can donate that food to those people who can't afford the food, for example, homeless people on the roads. This 'FeedingHope' is the website that can work to overcome the problem of food hunger, as 828 million people are going hungry and also roughly 43% of children in India are chronically undernourished. Feeding Hope is the website that will help NGOs to get in touch with more and more restaurants and make the processing work much easier using our website.

II. IS IT BENEFICIAL

Yes, of course, FeedingHope website is beneficial for both the poor and homeless people who can't afford food and it is beneficial for the restaurants, and hotels that dump large amounts of edible food that gets wasted on daily basis. It is beneficial for the environment, because once this food wastelands in landfills, it releases a powerful greenhouse gas – methane. This deadly gas with Carbon Dioxide and chlorofluorocarbons heats the earth's atmosphere, in the end, causing global warming.

III. WORKING OF THE WEBSITE SYSTEM

When the user first visits our Feeding Hope website, there will be a home page displaying the services, and information about our website, along with some extra informative sections such as blogs posted by us and other

users, trending news related to food hunger, success stories of the people around the world and in India. After visiting our website, the user who wants to become a part of our website, can register on the website as a volunteer or donor, filling in the information needed for authentication of the user. Now, the donor will be a restaurant and the volunteer will be an NGO, Only certified restaurants and NGOs can register here. If the user is already a part of our website, then he/she can log in on to the website to access it again. Now, the donor will make a request indicating that there is food available, then this request will be visible to the volunteer registered on the website. Any volunteer can accept the request and send an employee to pick up the food. The earlier request raised by a donor will be removed after getting accepted by a volunteer. For confirmation that food has been donated by homeless people, the volunteer can send pictures of it to the donor.

A. Software Requirement

- Operating System: Windows 10
- User Interface: HTML, CSS Client side.
- Scripting: JavaScript Programming Language, React Programming Language, PHP, Bootstrap
- Web Application: 000webhost, phpMyAdmin, Firebase
- Database : MySQL

B. Hardware Requirement

- Processor: Pentium IV Hard Disk: 40GB RAM: 512MB or more.

IV. PROPOSED SYSTEM

The website will help to connect more and more NGOs to restaurants and to collect the leftover food to donate to homeless people. The volunteer will get an request from the nearest restaurant about the leftovers and the respected NGO will accept the request and will proceed further and send the employee to do further donating work. This system makes the work easier to find people who are interested in doing social work.

V. FLOWCHARTS

Fig. 1. Home Page with registration, login, and footer.

Fig. 2. Food request and, accept the process.

VI. CONCLUSION

Through this project, we provide a way for various NGOs and restaurants to know each other. donating and volunteering to distribute the leftover food among homeless people. by such a way to become and motivate the youth to become responsible for the society and the environment. Managing the leftover food from such food media outlets by donating it instead of throwing it up.

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